

> DESIRE6G <

D6.5: Communication and Dissemination Plan (CODP) Report 2

HEU 6G SNS JU Project

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the final progress and achievements in WP6 in terms of Communication, Dissemination and Standardization, and outlines the ambitions after project completion.

Keywords

Communication, dissemination, standardization, open source.

Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms

RP	Reporting Period
3GPP	Third Generation Partnership Project
5G PPP	5G Public Private Partnership
AI	Artificial Intelligence
D6G	DESIRE6G
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IEEE	Institute of Electronics and Electrical Engineering
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IRTF	Internet Research Task Force
ITU-T	International Telecommunications Union – Telecommunications standardization sector
NMRG	Network Management Research Group
NFV	Network Functions Virtualization
ONAP	Open Network Automation Platform
ONOS	Open Network Operating System
OPNFV	Open Platform for NFV
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
OSM	Open Source MANO
SDN	Software Defined Networks
SDO	Standard Development Organization
TSG	Technical Specification Groups
WG	Working Group

Executive Summary

The main contributions of this document are:

- Final project progress overview, summarising achievements since project start and highlighting updates since Deliverable 6.3 (June 2024) [1] during the second reporting period.
- Project reach and impact over the full 36-month lifetime.
- Post-project ambitions, outlining next steps for communication, dissemination, standardisation, and long-term project reach.

Communication covers all activities aimed at promoting the project and its results beyond the project's own community. This includes explaining DESIRE6G (D6G) research in an accessible way to non-specialist audiences, such as the media and the general public. Dissemination focuses on raising awareness of the project's results within the relevant technical and scientific communities. In general, this will be done through scientific publications, and participation and organization of technical and scientific events. Although standardization belongs to exploitation, this deliverable also covers standardization, as it is not as sensitive to partners as exploitation, and it is important to report publicly on plans and early achievements.

The communication and dissemination plan (see Figure 1 for a complete scheme) started at the proposal stage with the non-disclosure agreement (NDA) signature and the identification of the various components of the project that could have an impact from a research point of view. Once the grant was awarded, the grant preparation phase, through the consortium agreement, served to define governance rules, including innovation management, and establishment of access rights, among others. After that, and from project start, the plan is structured in various phases.

During the *Raise Awareness* phase, at the initial stages of the project, the focus was on communication (e.g., setting up the web portal and social media accounts and high-level project presentations) to make the project known not just to the technical community but to a larger audience outside the project topics including the public. Dissemination and standardization activities also started in this phase with preliminary technical ideas.

In the *Presentation of Results* phase, dissemination and exploitation activities increased their intensity since the architecture and integration efforts had already produced meaningful results. Initial demonstrations of specific concepts of the architecture were performed during this phase. However, it is in the *Integrated Technical Demonstration* phase where demonstration activities involving multiple blocks of the architecture working in an integrated way are in focus.

Finally, in the *Long-lasting Impact* phase, the project generates an impact to other research or exploitation actions taken once the project is finished. This includes shaping the topics and framework of future research projects, exploiting DESIRE6G concepts in a market-oriented way by incorporating them in products and services, and leaving the DESIRE6G footprint in standards that include project contributions. The plan, set at the beginning of the project and reviewed through the project lifetime, not only defines the various activities undertaken, but it also defines target metrics for each of them.

Key contributions

Summary of the main contributions, take aways of the activities and metrics reported during the whole lifetime of the project:

Communication

- Utilization of branded promotion material, physically and digitally to raise awareness and create an identifiable project identity.
- Creation of content and regular update of project website, and on social media (LinkedIn, X and Bluesky), which has resulted in more than 97,471 visits to the website and a total combined of 809 followers across platforms.
- Communication talks and press releases for lay and expert stakeholder groups: students, authorities, and the SNS JU community.
- 35 videos created and available on our YouTube platform directed at differences audiences.

Dissemination

- 59 published or accepted scientific publications, (of which 55 peer-reviewed), some of them joint with other projects.
- 54 dissemination talks/ presentations to explain DESIRE6G and its concepts to a technical audience.
- 22 demos, 4 of which have been presented at flagship events (OFC 2024/2025, ICTON 2024/2025).

Standardization and Open Source

- Contributions: 17 to SDOs (3 approved/adopted) and 8 to open-source communities (4 accepted).
- Continuous monitoring of relevant SDOs (e.g., 3GPP, IETF, ETSI) and open-source projects for networking (e.g., TeraFlowSDN).
- Continuous review and update of the initial standardization roadmap according to the timelines of the SDOs and the project.

1. Introduction

The communication and dissemination plan of DESIRE6G includes the three following groups of activities:

- **Communication.** It includes all the activities related with the promotion of the project and its results beyond the project's own community. This includes communication of its research in a way that it is understood by non-specialist, e.g., the media and the public.
- **Dissemination.** It includes activities related with raising awareness of its results in a technical community working on the same research field. In general, this will be done through peer-reviewed publications in academic conferences and journals, and participation and organization of technical events.
- **Standardization and Open Source.** It covers monitoring and impact in standardization activities, and contributions to open source.

The communication and dissemination plan included all phases of the project (i.e., proposal, grant preparation, project lifetime, and after the project ends), where the focus is on activities tailored to each period. A summary of the plan is presented in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1: DESIRE6G COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

Figure 1 presents the various project milestones and deliverables directly related with the implementation of the plan as well as the various activities and phases during project execution. All activities have been carried out in parallel, with a different emphasis, depending on the phase of the project. D6.3 contains a detailed explanation of the different phases. In this document, we highlight the phases that have taken place primarily during the second reporting period of the project, namely the *Integrated Technical Demonstration* phase, where demonstration activities take more relevance and experimental results are obtained to validate the main architectural concepts of the project in an integrated way.

Finally, the project aims at having an impact after the project ends through other research projects, standardization contributions that include DESIRE6G concepts, or by influencing products and services of partner organizations. These activities conform the *Long-lasting Impact* phase.

As a reminder of the nature of the activities during the first reporting period, the initial phase of the project posed substantial effort in defining the standardization plan to be implemented during the project. This included the identification of relevant SDOs and open source projects, and the matching of project timelines with those of SDOs. Furthermore, such initial plan has been periodically updated to adapt to standardization interests and context variation.

In the same way, the whole communication and dissemination plan has also been periodically updated throughout the project, for example, because of the need of new activities to be defined or the emergence of new collaboration and dissemination opportunities. The following sections describe in detail the achievements for each of the activities. Note that this document is the final report of the project and therefore covers the whole duration of the project.

2. Achievements during project lifetime (January 2023 – December 2025)

2.1. Communication activities

In this section we report the achievements in terms of communication since the project start on 1st January 2023 until the final day of the project, on December 31st of 2025.

2.1.1. Branding

The logo, colours and fonts (Figure 2) were chosen at the beginning of the project in collaboration with a graphic designer, and they have been carried out to all online content and physical material in order to create a brand identity and remain recognizable. All deliverables, milestone reports, and presentations, even for internal use, also follow the official templates.

FIGURE 2: DESIRE6G'S MAIN LOGO AND HORIZONTAL LOGO (TOP); OFFICIAL COLOUR PALETTE AND FONTS FOR ALL DESIRE6G MATERIALS (BOTTOM)

2.1.2. Web, social media, and project communication material

Poster

The first project poster was presented at ETSI Research Conference (February 2023) during the official presentation of the first phase of SNS JU projects. Since then, partners have used the project logo and identity in their dissemination and communication around the world (Figure 3). Besides the well-known poster sessions at conferences, partners have also used posters for internal communication such as the Ericsson Open House Day in Budapest (Figure 4), and general public events like the Internet Festival in Pisa (Figure 5).

FIGURE 3: FIRST D6G POSTER (LEFT); P. GONZALEZ (UPC) AT OFC2024 (CENTER); A. ZAHIR (UC3M) AT EUCNC2024 (RIGHT)

FIGURE 4: ERICSSON'S HUNGARY DESIRE6G STAND AT OPEN HOUSE DAY IN BUDAPEST (APRIL 2024)

FIGURE 5: LAYMAN POSTER & DEMO 1 SET UP AT INTERNET FESTIVAL IN PISA (CNIT, SSSA) (OCTOBER 2025)

Leaflet

The project leaflet (Figure 6) was created to generate awareness about the project, and to communicate the project’s objectives and key innovations in an easy way. A QR code was added to the back of the brochure to generate traffic to the project’s website. Printed copies were distributed among D6G partners in June 2023, who through the time span of three years have displayed it at all kinds of events: conferences, workshops, panels, fairs, SNS events, etc. Additionally, special leaflets were created with PREDICT-6G for the joint booth and workshops at EuCNC in 2023, 2024 and 2025, and 6G-PDN 2024 and 2025.

Deep Programmability and Secure Distributed Intelligence for real-time E2E 6G Networks

PROJECT	VISION	USE CASES
<p>Project coordinator: Chrysa Papagianni, PhD University of Amsterdam</p> <p>Technical coordinator: Gergely Pongracz, MSc Ericsson Hungary</p> <p>Duration: 01/01/2023 - 31/12/2025</p> <p>Cost: 6.227.919€</p> <p>Follows us on: desire6g.eu @DESIRE6G_EU @DESIRE6G </p>	<p>VISION</p> <p>Design and develop a zero-touch control, management & orchestration platform, with native integration of AI, to support verticals with extreme application requirements over a performant, measurable and programable data plane.</p>	<p>USE CASES</p> <p>We focus on two representative 6G use cases targeting extreme key performance indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Digital Twin ▪ Intelligent and resilient VR/AR applications with perceived zero latency
<p>KEY INNOVATIONS</p> <p>DESIRE6G will re-architect mobile networks targeting real time autonomic networking via:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A hybrid architecture employing lightweight centralized management & orchestration, with distributed intelligent control. 2. An E2E programmable user plane using a generic hardware abstraction layer, supporting heterogeneous systems e.g., GPUs, TPUs, FPGAs, SOCs. 		
<p>PARTNERS</p>		

FIGURE 6: PROJECT LEAFLET (MAY 2023)

Website

The project website <https://desire6g.eu/> was created at the beginning of the project using the DESIRE6G's brand identity and launched to the public on March 30th, 2023. Figure 7 shows the landing page (as of December 2025), containing the title, overarching objective, and shortcuts to main topics such as consortium composition, the project's vision and the Demo videos. The main page also includes project details, i.e.: the duration, total cost and grant amount, as well as the Grant number and official acknowledgement to the funding from Horizon Europe and SNS JU.

The website is DESIRE6G's most complete source of information, and it is updated weekly with the latest publications, presentations, communication materials and events. The Introduction video created for both an expert and general audience was added to the front page to attract viewers in July 2024. More recently, in July 2025, a new page "[Demo and PoC Videos](#)" was created and added to the top menu to guide visitors to some of the main project results. In December 2025, a new section called "[Contributions](#)" was added to highlight the Standard contributions and Open-Source contributions stemming from the project.

The statistics from the project website were collected in June 2023 and later in June 2024 (reported in D6.3 CODEP1) to monitor the engagement throughout the project's lifetime. As the project ends, we assess positively its performance, highlighted by the increase in traffic generated to the website in the past 18 months, as shown below. Data retrieved as of 19 December 2025.

TABLE 1: WEBSITE TOTAL VISITS AND VISITORS

	Total values June 2023	Total values June 2024	Total values December 2025
Total visits	1601	22,891	97,411
Total visitors	788	9,770	35,939

A significant rise in unique visitors was observed during the second half of the project, with more than 26,000 new visitors since June 2024, compared to almost 10,000 reached during the first 18 months. Importantly, many of them are recurring, and together have amounted to over 74,000 visits in RP2. This underscores the value of keeping the website regularly updated and reflects the sustained effort to drive traffic through social media channels.

FIGURE 7: DESIRE6G WEBSITE LANDING PAGE (DECEMBER 2025)

The distribution of visits and visitors in Figure 8 indicates increased activity coinciding with LinkedIn posts that promoted the website and tagged multiple people and institutions, such as September 2025. A decline in views is observed during periods when such posts were not published.

FIGURE 8: CHART OF DESIRE6G.EU VISITS AND VISITORS BY WEEK, FROM 1 JANUARY 2025 TO NOVEMBER 2025

Table 2 shows the most visited pages on the website organized based on the ranking from June 2024. The order has remained the same for the most part; while the landing Home page remains the most visited by far, the contact page is now in second place, followed by the News section, which makes sense because that is the most shared page on social media. The most viewed News posts are shown in Figure 11.

TABLE 2: EVOLUTION OF THE MOST VISITED PAGES AND TOTAL VISITS ON DESIRE6G.EU AS OF 19 DECEMBER 2025

#	Page title	June 2023	June 2024	December 2025
1	Home Page	955	7,718	31,310
2	News	-	2,310	11,151
3	Contact	29	1,878	18,993
4	Deliverables	53	644	2,125
5	Consortium	77	595	2,078
6	Publications	57	588	1,783
7	Vision	44	511	1,816
8	Workshop 6G-PDN	34	499	(2 nd 6G-PDN) 1,716
9	Presentations	-	471	1,481
10	Project	88	459	1,626

It is worth highlighting that the number of visits to the page about the second 6G-PDN workshop in 2024 ([6G Programmable Deterministic Networking with AI](#)) received more than three times more visits than the first edition in 2023 (1,716 vs 599), suggesting more interest or a more effective promotion campaign.

Additionally, a news item was added almost monthly to the blog (<https://desire6g.eu/blog/>) reporting on highlights such as newsflashes, workshop organization, face-to-face meetings, and upcoming events (see overview in Figure 10). Figure 9 shows the performance of the blog since the 1st of March, with a total of 24 posts, 387 visitors and 8,363 views. Figure 11 shows the most visited blog posts during the project's lifetime.

FIGURE 9: PERFORMANCE OF DESIRE6G'S BLOG. BLUE BARS ARE POSTS. PURPLE LINE ARE VIEWS. FROM 1 MARCH 2023 TO 19 DECEMBER 2025.

News

DESIRE6G COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES BRING 6G CLOSER TO SOCIETY

October 27, 2025

As part of its mission to connect cutting-edge 6G research with society, DESIRE6G recently took part in two major outreach events – the Internet Festival 2025 in Pisa, Italy, and Researchers' Night in Budapest, Hungary. Both initiatives showcased how 6G technologies can be made tangible, interactive, and accessible to all audiences. 🦾 Augmented Reality and...

NEWSFLASH: DESIRE6G DEMONSTRATOR UPDATE

September 25, 2025

DESIRE6G is entering the last phase of the project, with two large-scale demonstrators successfully integrated and operational. These demos validate the project's key innovations and offer tangible examples of how programmable, intelligent, and distributed 6G infrastructures can support emerging mission-critical applications. Demo 1 – Cooperative Surveillance with Augmented Reality Status: Fully integrated across two sites...

DESIRE6G AT IETF 123 HACKATHON: ADVANCING DETERMINISTIC NETWORKING WITH IN-BAND TELEMETRY

August 13, 2025

On 19–20 July 2025, the DESIRE6G project took part in the IETF 123 Hackathon in Madrid, an event bringing together experts and developers to collaborate on advancing Deterministic Networking (DetNet). Organized by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF), the hackathon fostered technical exchange, rapid prototyping, and real-time testing of new ideas. As part of the...

DESIRE6G AT EUCNC & 6G SUMMIT 2025

April 29, 2025

DESIRE6G will make its final public appearance at the EuCNC & 6G Summit 2025, taking place June 3–6 in Poznań, Poland. As the project nears the end, we are proud to present the most advanced versions of our two flagship demos and share our key technical contributions with the 6G community. Joint Booth, alongside PREDICT-6G...

DESIRE6G CONTRIBUTES TO KEY 6G WHITE PAPERS

February 26, 2025

Over the past year, DESIRE6G members have been actively engaged in 6G SNS IU and 6G-IA working groups, collaborating with experts to shape the future of next-generation networks. We are proud to have contributed to the development of six white papers that address critical aspects of 6G, from AI-driven innovations to security, network management, and...

WHITE PAPER ON THE EUROPEAN VISION FOR THE 6G NETWORK ECOSYSTEM

November 27, 2024

The 6G IA Vision Working Group are pleased to present their White Paper on The EUROPEAN VISION For The 6G NETWORK ECOSYSTEM. This white paper highlights the importance of creating a unified 6G vision, driven by key stakeholders worldwide, towards a single global consensus. Specifically, the European perspective, as represented by the 6G Smart Networks...

ENHANCEMENTS TOWARDS MANAGEMENT OF TIME-SENSITIVE NETWORKS

October 14, 2024

A joint webinar with DESIRE6G, PREDICT6G and DETERMINISTIC6G on 22 October: 'Enhancements towards management of time-sensitive networks' More information here

NEWS FLASH: DESIRE6G FIRST 18 MONTHS: KEY INNOVATIONS AND STANDARDIZATION EFFORTS

October 14, 2024

DESIRE6G Key Innovations The DESIRE6G project has made significant strides in its first reporting period (Jan 2023 – June 2024), working on innovations aimed at revolutionizing 6G networks. Here's a snapshot of the major advances: More information regarding the respective innovations is available in DESIRE6G's technical deliverables (<https://desire6g.eu/deliverables/>) Standardization Efforts Standardization is one of the...

HALFWAY THROUGH DESIRE6G: A LOOK AT OUR ACHIEVEMENTS

June 28, 2024

DESIRE6G, a SNS IU and Horizon Europe project aimed at revolutionizing next-generation wireless communication systems, has reached the halfway point of its 3 year timeline. We take this opportunity to highlight our main achievements. WP2: Requirements and Architecture Design In WP2 we have successfully defined five use cases along with their Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)...

6G PROGRAMMABLE DETERMINISTIC WEBINAR SERIES

June 13, 2024

FIGURE 10: OVERVIEW OF THE NEWS SECTION (BLOG)

Top Contents

Most Popular

Most Commented

-

DESIRE6G meets in Amsterdam for the 4th Consortium meeting
 932 views
-

News Flash: DESIRE6G First 18 Months: Key Innovations and Standardization Efforts
 700 views
-

Press release: PREDICT-6G and DESIRE6G co-organise the "6G-PDN Workshop" at MobiHoc 2023
 533 views
-

From vision to reality: DESIRE6G first year overview
 498 views
-

6G Programmable Deterministic Webinar series
 420 views

FIGURE 11: MOST VISITED POSTS IN DESIRE6G.EU/NEWS SINCE MARCH 2023 TO DECEMBER 2025

Social Media

DESIRE6G has been active on social media via LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter), and Bluesky. Social media accounts are used mostly to inform the public about new publications, deliverables and presentations as well as upcoming events. Additionally, it is also used to engage with fellow SNS project and the wider (6G) networks research community. Social media platforms have shown to be useful to disseminate project results aimed at an expert audience, which interacts and generates an active community. Nevertheless, DESIRE6G has also taken part in communication activities aimed at a non-expert audience, which have been promoted through these platforms. On top of that, from Task 6.1, project partners have contributed to create layman content to capture a broader audience and to bring 6G research further.

Below are shown the aggregated metrics from DESIRE6G's social media accounts. LinkedIn remains the most successful platform in terms of numbers of followers, i.e.: 642 versus 133 (X) and 34 (Bluesky) (see Table 3). The simplest explanation for the difference is that not only are there more SNS projects present and active on LinkedIn, but also individual project members have their own account, which they use to announce their publications and conferences, as well as to engage with project pages. This is not the case for X, and Bluesky. Moreover, the character limit in the latter two platforms is not well suited to share a scientific abstract or a Call for Papers.

TABLE 3: METRICS OF DESIRE6G'S SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS AS OF DECEMBER 2025

	LinkedIn	X (Twitter)	Bluesky
Followers in December 2025	642	133	34
Following	104	176	78
Posts	No data. Estimate ~400	242	31

LinkedIn Analytics <https://www.linkedin.com/company/desire6g-project>

Since the publication of D6.3 in June 2024, DESIRE6G's growth and engagement on LinkedIn has slowed down, as shown in Table 4. While from 2023 to 2024 it gained 347 followers, the increase was just 142 followers in the last 18 months. Similarly, the number of views, visitors and clicks decreased sharply from one year to another. This seems to be a generalized trend among SNS JU LinkedIn pages, as shown by the ranking of growth of competitors in the last 365 days, in Figure 12. DESIRE6G's leading position across metrics, proves that despite high activity in terms of page posts and engagement, acquisition of new followers slows down after a while.

TABLE 4: @DESIRE6G_EU LINKEDIN ANALYTICS

	June 2023	June 2024	December 2025
Followers	153	500	642
Visitors	January to June 2023	June 2023 to 2024	Last 365 days
Page views	354	1,436	552
Unique visitors	174	500	267
Custom button clicks	30	20	0
Content	January to June 2023	June 2023 to 2024	Last 365 days
Reactions	364	1,235	963
Comments	7	20	12
Reposts	31	52	9

FIGURE 12: RANKING OF SNS PROJECTS METRICS IN THE LAST YEAR. NEW FOLLOWERS (LEFT), TOTAL POSTS (CENTER), ENGAGEMENT (RIGHT)

Interestingly, the country where DESIRE6G’s followers are based correlates with the consortium partners’ nationality. For instance, Madrid houses four consortium partners, and it’s the area with the greatest number of followers.

TABLE 5: LINKEDIN FOLLOWERS’ DEMOGRAPHICS BY LOCATION IN NOVEMBER 2025

Metropolitan city Area	Numbers of followers	Percentage of total
Madrid Area, Spain	54	8.5%
The Randstad, Netherlands,	20	3.1%
Greater Istanbul, Türkiye	17	2.7%
Pisa, Italy	15	2.4%
Barcelona, Spain	14	2.2%
Great Bengaluru Area, India	14	2.2%
Greater Delhi Area, India	13	2%
Budapest, Hungary	13	2%
Athens, Greece	12	1.9%
Greater Paris, France	9	1.4%

X (former Twitter) discontinuation https://twitter.com/DESIRE6G_EU

During the plenary meeting in Leganés (Madrid) of February 2025, the consortium decided to transition DESIRE6G's social media presence from X (formerly Twitter) to Bluesky. This decision followed growing concerns across the research and innovation community regarding the evolving moderation policies, discourse climate, and content governance on X, which were increasingly seen as inconsistent with the project's values of openness, inclusivity, and evidence-based communication. The decision was announced via tweet, but the account has not been closed, so it serves as a catalogue of the project's results and events up until March 2025.

In line with many other projects and individuals who decided to leave X, the number of followers has dropped from 158 to 133 in the last 18 months.

TABLE 6: @DESIRE6G X ANALYTICS TOTAL VALUES

	June 2023	June 2024	December 2025
Followers	42	158	133
Following	52	176	176
Tweets	72	226	242

Bluesky

DESIRE6G posted on Bluesky for the first time on March 20, 2025, using a group photo taken at IMDEA/5TONIC in Leganés during the face-to-face meeting hosted by UC3M in February 2025 (Figure 13). Since then, growth has been slow and engagement very limited, which is very similar to other SNS JU projects. This issue was raised by the leader of Task 6.1 during the SNS Communication Taskforce meeting in October 2025, and the experience turned out to be the same for all the other projects in attendance.

FIGURE 13: FIRST DESIRE6G POST ON BLUESKY

TABLE 7: BLUESKY ANALYTICS

Total values December 2025	
Followers	34
Following	78
Posts	31

Interaction in social media

The participation from the consortium members from their own social media accounts has been crucial to achieve the online presence of DESIRE6G. Through posting and tagging @DESIRE6G in their own profiles and liking and reposting DESIRE6G’s posts, the page gained significant popularity. Moreover, interaction with other SNS JU projects and official accounts of organizations (such as SNS JU, 6G IA, 6G Hexa-XII flagship project, PREDICT-6G, and DETERMINISTIC6G) generated additional traffic.

YouTube channel www.youtube.com/@desire6g_eu

DESIRE6G's YouTube channel was also created at the beginning of the project to host all the videos, both dissemination and communication. Figure 14 shows the updated main page as of November 2025.

FIGURE 14: MAIN PAGE YOUTUBE CHANNEL

The first video (DESIRE6G Introduction video, shown in Figure 7, was uploaded to the channel on April 2nd, 2024. This video was created together with a professional animation company, which supported us in creating the script, drafted together with WP leaders. This video (available [here](#)), gives some context about the project, the need for 6G research, and the key objectives, all understandable for the general public. In addition, the content goes in depth in the technical innovations to be developed in the project, aimed at an expert audience. At the end, the video explains the role of SNS JU and the ecosystem of SNS projects, working to achieve European 6G network by 2030. As of November 2025, the Introduction video has been the most popular of all, with 326 views.

On top of that, in D6.3 CODEP 1 (June 2024), we reported 11 more videos uploaded (shown in Figure 15): three partner introductions, a series focused on introducing partners' views and interest on the project, two testbeds presentations of 5TONIC and ARNO, and five preliminary demos.

FIGURE 15: OVERVIEW VIDEOS UPLOADED ON YOUTUBE IN RP1 (UNTIL JUNE 2024)

Figure 16 shows all the 21 videos uploaded to YouTube in RP2 (July 2024 to December 2025), including more partner introductions, five Proof-of-Concepts, three updated project Demos (Augmented Reality and Real-Time Robot Digital Twins), and three additional demos by UVA.

Note that several videos are planned for publication over the next few days, including additional partner presentation videos, and most significantly, final demos and PoC videos. We expect the latter to be one of the main legacies for the research community as an entry point to learn about the main achievements and technology of the project, serving as a link to the more detailed technical deliverables where interested stakeholders and researchers would find additional information.

FIGURE 16: OVERVIEW VIDEOS UPLOADED IN RP2 (UNTIL DECEMBER 2025)

YouTube analytics

The metrics in Table 8 show that subscribers have doubled over the second half of the project's lifetime, accompanied by a sharp increase in views, from 500 to over 3,000.

TABLE 8: YOUTUBE ANALYTICS. ACCUMULATED VALUES FROM JUNE 2024 AND DECEMBER 2025

	June 2024	December 2025
Subscribers	14	61
Views	511	3,408
Videos	12	35
Shorts	0	2
Total watch time (hours)	9.7	42

As shown in the top graph in Figure 17, most views originated from the Shorts feed, driven by two short vertical videos (a few seconds each) recorded at 5TONIC and ARNO (see

Figure 18). This reflects the general trend of YouTube, with Shorts getting more views than regular (long) videos. When focusing on external sources only (bottom graph), we observe that traffic came mostly from LinkedIn (36%), and Google search (7%), again reflecting the importance of DESIRE6G's LinkedIn page as a way to attract and channel visitors to other platforms.

FIGURE 17: VIEWS BY TRAFFIC SOURCE. TOP: ALL SOURCES: BOTTOM: BREAKDOWN OF EXTERNAL SOURCES

FIGURE 18: DESIRE6G YOUTUBE SHORTS

The audience analysis based on age and gender shown in Figure 19 presents a striking gender-based difference, as 91,7% of the total viewers are male. This is in line with the general misrepresentation of women in STEM and specially in the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) field (Eurostat, European Commission, 2024¹).

FIGURE 19: AUDIENCE BY AGE AND GENDER (NOVEMBER 2025)

2.1.3. Communication Talks and other actions

Press Releases

During the first reporting period, from January 2023 to July 2024, press releases focused on the initial promotion of the project start, the organization of the first joint workshop 6G-PDN and the summary of technical achievements at 12 and 18 months (see Table 9). The first news piece by the University of Amsterdam, with an interview to the project coordinator Dr. Chrysa Papagianni, is still accessible [here](#) [2]. From July 2024 until December 2025, we have published three more press releases highlighting the main advancements from the project i.e.: standardization activities, main technical results, and project related demos. A final press release is planned to be published in early 2026, summarizing the general impact of the project's results and innovations on 6G research.

¹ https://doi.org/10.2908/ISOC_SKI_ITSEX

TABLE 9: OVERVIEW PRESS RELEASES/ NEWS FLASHES BY DESIRE6G

Title (link to document included)	Publication date
The final chapter: DESIRE6G's impact on 6G research (in planning)	early 2026
Newsflash: DESIRE6G Demonstrator Update	September 2025
DESIRE6G Key Achievements	August 2025
News Flash: DESIRE6G First 18 Months: Key Innovations and Standardization Efforts	October 2024
Halfway through DESIRE6G: a look at our achievements	June 2024
DESIRE6G: One year review	December 2023
PREDICT-6G and DESIRE6G co-organise "6G-PDN Workshop" at MobiHoc 2023	November 2023
EU project DESIRE6G lays foundation for 6G system architecture	June 2023

Communication Talks and other actions

Previously in D6.1 [3] and D6.3 [1] we reported Table 10 below which summarizes all the communication activities performed from January 2023 to June 2024 by the consortium and project partners individually or collaboratively.

TABLE 10: COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES ABOUT DESIRE6G FROM JANUARY 2023 TO JUNE 2024

Communication action	Partner
January 2023 to June 2023	
Internal university newsletter about the project an interview with Project coordinator	UVA
Project presentation at JU SNS Lunch Webinar	UVA
Science Fair in Madrid and news item on university website	UC3M
Project Coordinator video at EuCNC2023, accessible at 6G SNS YouTube channel	UVA
DESIRE6G presentation in the lecture about Cellular Networks (part of Advanced Networking Masters Course)	UVA

LinkedIn promotion of published open access scientific articles	CNIT
DESIRE6G presentation during Ericsson Open House Day	ERI-HU
DESIRE6G presentation to Hungarian authorities within Ericsson's R&D portfolio	ERI-HU
Articles on university and faculty website and newsletter	ELTE
Marketing activities achieved featuring in 14 national ICT/ business digital portals	ELTE
Internal and external Ericsson Research Türkiye newsletters	EBY
Project presentation and news for the Turkish Research Council	EBY
DESIRE6G presentations for Turk Telekom Innovation Directorate & Turkcell Academy	EBY
DESIRE6G project presentation in the lecture about Algorithmic Methods for Mathematical Models (part of Master in Innovation and Research in Informatics)	UPC
LinkedIn promotion of the project, publications, events and collaboration between partners	NVIDIA
Project explanation in the company's website	TSS
Project presentation during 5G/6G Seasonal School	SSSA
June 2023 to June 2024	
Seminar "Towards extreme network KPIs with programmability in 6G" at HyNet lab, University of Maryland, 19 October 2023.	UVA
Project presentation DESIRE6G "Towards Extreme Network KPIs with Deep Programmability in 6G" in the 6G SNS JU brokerage event in Istanbul.	UVA
Press release First year overview of DESIRE6G	UVA, ERI-HU, UC3M, TID, CNIT, NUBIS
HTE Seminar Budapest about the project goals and the proposed data plane concepts	ELTE
4th Preparatory workshop for the Hungarian EU presidency, 05 December 2023 - 15 minutes talk about the SNS program and showing DESIRE6G as an example	ELTE
6G Work Group meeting of the Hungarian 5G Coalition, 06 December 2023 - 15 minutes talk about the goals of DESIRE6G	ELTE
LinkedIn post about ARNO testbed	CNIT, SSSA
YouTube video introducing ARNO testbed and WP5 federated testbeds	CNIT, SSSA
Internal communication of project results to internal stakeholders.	NEC

Presentation “Automatizing CyberThreat Intelligence” at Universidad de Comillas for the Master’s program Cybersecurity.	NEC
Presentation for Master students at University of Amsterdam	ERI-HU
YouTube video about 5TONIC lab and its use in the project	UC3M
Content about the project objectives published in the TUBITAK’s newsletter	EBY
Supported the SNS Brokerage Event organized by TUBITAK and Sabanci University in Istanbul	EBY
DESIRE6G was represented in the 6G-IA WiTaR working group	EBY
Organization of the joint booth at EuCNC2024	UC3M, UVA, CNIT
Internal dissemination within Telefonica group.	TID
DESIRE6G was introduced as part of the initiatives carried out in Telefonica for facing advanced guaranteed services in the talk entitled “Telefónica initiative for E2E latency and jitter analysis” at the second edition of the webinar event Understanding Latency	TID
Co-creation of website content about demos and OFC2024 presence	UPC, NVIDIA, SSSA, UVA
Creation of communication material for EuCNC2024: news, LinkedIn event and social media activation and strong interaction with PREDICT-6G	UVA
LinkedIn post about collaborative 6G research with D6G partners and dissemination of publications and achievements	NVIDIA, ACC
Offered VR experience to EuCNC visitors at D6G booth and posted on social media	SSSA, CNIT
Presented DESIRE6G during INCYBER Fair	TSS
Made DESIRE6G t-shirts to wear during the demo sessions at OFC2024	UPC
Presented D6G and brought leaflets to KubeCON and FOSDEM2024	NUBIS
Weekly LinkedIn activity to support project posts	ACC
Organization of EuCNC joint booth together with PREDICT-6G, photo and video recording at the venue and social media activity during the conference	UC3M
LinkedIn content based on dissemination talks and publications	SSSA
Talk on 5G applications at the workshop called “Robotica e macchine intelligenti” at the “Festival della Robotica” for general public	SSSA, CNIT
DESIRE6G robotic dog and AR experience at EuCNC 2024 booth	UC3M, ELTE, NUBIS, UVA
Spanish network-related podcasts: RTS/CTS” (Spotify) and ”Tecnología en 5 minutos”, episode devoted to 6G” (Podtail)	UC3M

“Innovation and testbed projects for the evolution of mobile networks” talk during Telefonica’s 100 th anniversary event	UC3M
YouTube video introducing the partner, motivation and contribution to the project	TSS, UC3M, EBY
Video of Technical coordinator from EuCNC on his view of D6G’s key objectives	ERI-HU

In Table 11 below we report the communication activities that have taken place in RP2, until the date of publication of this report.

TABLE 11: COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES FROM JULY 2024 TO DECEMBER 2025

Communication action	Partner
July 2024 to December 2025	
C. Papagianni participated in the Dutch Beyond 5G/6G innovation mission to Japan, led by the Holland High Tech sector and the Dutch government in May 2025 (around Expo 2025 Osaka), focused on forging strategic partnerships	UVA
Partner introduction videos explaining their contribution to DESIRE6G	UOU, UVA, ACC, CNIT, NEC, ELTE, NUBIS, SSSA, UPC, TID, UPM
Demonstration 1 video: Augmented Reality with perceived zero latency (October 2024)	CNIT
Demonstration 2 video: Real-time Digital Twins (September 2024)	UC3M
News Flash: DESIRE6G First 18 Months: Key Innovations and Standardization Efforts	UVA, TID, ERI-HU, UC3M
Video for YouTube shorts “Robotic Dog at 5TONIC” (March 2025)	UVA
Communication booth at innovation fair Beyond2025 in Athens (April 2025)	NUBIS
Project summary for Annual 6G SNS Journal – 2025 Edition	UVA
Social media updates and photos about consortium meeting in Pisa	UVA
Creation of PoC videos for YouTube and social media promotion	TSS
Content and photos from presentations at ICTON and OECC/PSC for social media	UPC, UVA
Video for YouTube shorts “Drone and VR set I D6G Demo 1” (July 2025)	UVA
Promotion of SNS Journal 2025 on DESIRE6G’s LinkedIn page (August 2025)	UVA
IETF 123 Hackathon content and photos for social media posts	TID
Press release of DESIRE6G Key Achievements, posted on website and social media	UVA, ERI-HU
LinkedIn post and photos about poster presentation at SIGCOMM	UVA

Newsflash: DESIRE6G Demonstrator Update, posted on website and social media	UVA, ERI-HU, CNIT, UC3M
General public Demo presentation during Researchers' Night 2025 in Budapest	ELTE
LinkedIn content and photos for the generation of posts about communication	ELTE
Demo1 presentation for the general public at Internet Festival 2025, Pisa	CNIT, SSSA
LinkedIn posts about communication activities for the general public	CNIT
LinkedIn posts about participation in N2WOMEN Panel at WIMOB conference	UVA
News items about DESIRE6G communication activities in the blog's website	UVA
DESIRE6G presented in general public Research Fair "UPM Conecta"	UPM
Internal presentation to business unit on "Experimenting Deterministic Communication Services on the Operator Side"	TID
Project coordinator presented the scope and results of DESIRE6G to multiple partners, such as a workshop organized between UVA and Instituto Federal da Paraíba	UVA

2.2. Dissemination activities

In this section we report the dissemination activities of the project. DESIRE6G has carried out multiple dissemination activities, leveraging every opportunity at a project and individual partner level to spread the project results, this included presentations in multiple workshops, conferences, seminars and fora.

2.2.1. Publications and technical dissemination

Table 12 presents peer-reviewed articles in scientific journals and studies/demos/posters in scientific conferences from January 2023 to December 2025. Item titles contain links to the articles in Zenodo. Only published or accepted publications are shown.

TABLE 12: DESIRE6G PUBLICATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC JOURNALS AND CONFERENCES (CONF)

#	Type	Title	Publication/Conference	Publication date
1	conf	P4-Based INT Implementation on FPGAs: A Hardware-Accelerated Approach	Conf. Innovation in Clouds, Internet and Networks (ICIN 2026)	December 2025
2	conf	6GUPF: A DPU-based Programmable User Plane Function for Enhanced Flow-based QoS	IEEE Global Communications Conference (Globecom 2025)	December 2025
3	conf	QueuePilot: Towards Adaptive Queue Scheduling via Live Digital Twins	International Conference on emerging Networking EXperiments and Technologies (CoNEXT '25)	November 2025
4	conf	Reconstructing LLM Training Workloads: A Topology- and Model-aware Network Tester	International Conference on emerging Networking EXperiments and Technologies (CoNEXT '25)	November 2025
5	journal	Hybrid-Hierarchical Synchronization for Resilient Large-Scale SDN Architectures	IEEE Access	November 2025
6	conf	LLM-Based Optimization Algorithm Selection for High-Performance Networks Orchestration	Workshops of the International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis	November 2025

7	conf	End-User Performance Isolation at Scale in Access Aggregation Networks	IEEE Conference on Network Function Virtualization and Software Defined Networks (NFV-SDN 2025)	November 2025
8	conf	POSTER: FlexUP: Breaking Up the CU-UP to Speed Up the RAN	ACM Interest Group on Data Communication (SIGCOMM 2025)	September 2025
9	conf	Augmented Reality in the DESIRE6G Cloud-native and Programmable Infrastructure with Multi-Agent System and Pervasive Monitoring	IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking (CSCN 2025)	October 2025
10	journal	DETROIT: Decomposition Techniques for a Hierarchy of 6G Network Intent Management Functions	Computer Networks	August 2025
11	conf	Programmable & Trustworthy Data Paths for Sovereign Network Services	Int. Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON 2025)	July 2025
12	conf	On the Benefits of Multi-Agent Systems for Operational Expenditure Savings	Int. Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON 2025)	July 2025
13	conf	Intelligent Reconfiguration of Distributed Control of 6G Network Services	Int. Conference on Photonics in Switching and Computing (PSC 2025)	July 2025
14	conf	Empowering 6G Communication Service Providers: A Seamless SLA-to-Intent Translation Framework	Conference on Innovation in Clouds, Internet and Networks (ICIN 2025)	June 2025
15	conf	Lightweight Sandboxing for Cloud-native 6G Services and Applications	IEEE Int. Workshop on Computer Aided Modeling and Design of Communication Links and Networks (CAMAD 2024)	June 2025
16	conf	Service and Resource Management Enablers for 6G Networks (invited paper about SNS Reliable SoftNet WG whitepaper)	EuCNC & 6G Summit 2025	June 2025
17	journal	DESIRE6G - Meeting extreme KPIs through Deep Programmability in 6G AI-Native Systems (not peer reviewed)	European 6G Annual Journal 2025	May 2025

18	journal	A Deep RL Approach on Task Placement and Scaling of Edge Resources for Cellular Vehicle-to-Network Service Provisioning	IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management	May 2025
19	conf	RAILS: Risk-Aware Iterated Local Search for Joint SLA Decomposition and Service Provider Management in Multi-Domain Networks	IEEE Int. Conference on High Performance Switching and Routing (HPSR 2025)	May 2025
20	conf	Online SLA Decomposition: Enabling Real-Time Adaptation to Evolving Network Systems	EuCNC & 6G Summit 2025	April 2025
21	conf	In-band Collection and Control of End-to-end Latency in Programmable Packet-Optical Networks	Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC 2025)	March 2025
22	conf	Lightweight INT on the Tofino programmable switch	ACM MobiCom 2024	December 2024
23	conf	Utilizing Hybrid P4 Solutions to Enhance 5G gNB with Data Plane Programmability	IFIP Wireless and Mobile Networking Conference	November 2024
24	conf	Intent-Based Management for Industrial Automation	IEEE Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA 2024)	October 2024
25	conf	P4-MTAGG - a Framework for Multi-Tenant P4 Network Devices	IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking (CNSM 2024)	October 2024
26	conf	P4-MTAGG - a Framework for Multi-Tenant P4 Network Devices	WueWoWAS'24	September 2024
27	conf	Utilizing Hybrid P4 Solutions to Enhance 5G gNB with Data Plane Programmability	WueWoWas'24	September 2024
28	conf	Effectiveness of Confidentiality-Preserving Clustering Algorithms for Soft Failure Detection in Optical Networks	Int. Conference on High Performance Switching and Routing (HSPR2024)	August 2024

29	conf	Edge Orchestration Framework for AI-assisted Link Failure Forecasting and Recovery	Int. Conference on High Performance Switching and Routing (HSPR2024)	July 2024
30	conf	5GDAD: A Deep Learning Approach for DDoS Attack Detection in 5G P4-based UPF	Int. Conference on High Performance Switching and Routing (HSPR2024)	July 2024
31	conf	Augmented Reality App with AI-based Pervasive Latency Monitoring of RAN and Programmable Metro Packet-Optical Networks	Int. Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON 2024)	July 2024
32	conf	In-network Control for Flow Steering	Int. Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON 2024)	June 2024
33	journal	P4 FANET In-band Telemetry (FINT) for AI-assisted wireless link failure forecasting and recovery	Computer Networks	June 2024
34	journal	DESIRE6G: Meeting extreme KPIs through Deep Programmability in 6G AI-Native Systems (not peer reviewed)	European 6G Annual Journal 2024	June 2024
35	conf	Near Real-Time Autonomous Multi-Flow Routing with Dynamic Optical Bypass Management	Int. Conference on Optical Network Design and Modelling (ONDM 2024)	May 2024
36	conf	Header Proposal for the DetNet Application Layer	Int Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON 2024)	May 2024
37	conf	Reliability in deterministic networks: Comparison of FRER (TSN) and PREOF (DetNet)	Int Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON 2024)	May 2024
38	journal	BayGO: Decentralized Bayesian Learning and Information-Aware Graph Optimization Framework	IEEE Signal Processing	April 2024
39	conf	Distributed Genuine Intelligence: From Agent Integrity to Secure Inter-Agent Communications	European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC24 & 6G SUMMIT)	April 2024
40	conf	Distributed Multi-Agent System fed with Telemetry Data for Near-Real-Time Service Operation	Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC24)	January 2024
41	conf	Deployment of Secure Machine Learning Pipelines for Near-Real-Time Control of 6G Network Services	Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC24)	January 2024
42	journal	Autonomous Flow Routing for Near Real-Time Quality of Service Assurance	IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management	December 2023

43	journal	Radio Propagation Digital Twin Aided Multi-Point Transmission With In-Network Dynamic On-Off Switching	IEEE Access	November 2023
44	conf	Performance evaluation of Private and Public Blockchains for multi-cloud service federation	Int. Conference on Distributed Computing and Networking (ICDCN24)	November 2023
45	conf	Towards extreme network KPIs with programmability in 6G	Int. Symposium on Theory, Algorithmic Foundations, and Protocol Design for Mobile Networks and Computing (MobiHoc23)	October 2023
46	conf	In-Network Quality Control of IP Camera Streams	Int. Symposium on Theory, Algorithmic Foundations, and Protocol Design for Mobile Networks and Computing (MobiHoc23)	October 2023
47	conf	Integration of Network Slice Controller for Enhanced Intent-Based Networking in 5G/6G Networks	Int. Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking (MobiCom23)	October 2023
48	conf	Federated Learning Gamed for Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces via Causal Representations	IEEE Global Communications Conference (Globecom23)	September 2023
49	journal	SLA Decomposition for Network Slicing: A Deep Neural Network Approach	IEEE Networking Letters	August 2023
50	conf	Dynamic Traffic Prediction Model Retraining for Autonomous Network Operation	Int. Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON23)	July 2023
51	conf	DIN: A Decentralized Inexact Newton Algorithm for Consensus Optimization	IEEE Int. Conference on Communications (ICC23)	June 2023
52	journal	DESIRE6G: Deep Programmability & Secure Distributed Intelligence for Real-Time E2E 6G Networks (not peer reviewed)	European 6G Annual Journal (SNS)	May 2023
53	conf	Comparison of Statistical and Machine Learning-Based Approaches for Telemetry Data Size Reduction	Int. Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON23)	May 2023
54	conf	Securing Multi-Agent Systems for Near Real-Time Control of 6G Services	EuCNC23 & 6G SUMMIT	May 2023
55	journal	P4-assisted seamless migration of serverless applications towards the edge continuum	Future Generation Computer Systems	April 2023

56	conf	Pervasive Monitoring and Distributed Intelligence for 6G Near Real-Time Operation	European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC23 & 6G SUMMIT)	April 2023
57	journal	P4 Telemetry collector	Computer Networks	March 2023
58	conf	V2N Service Scaling with Deep Reinforcement Learning	IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium	February 2023
59	journal	Deep Learning-Based Adaptive Compression and Anomaly Detection for Smart B5G Use Cases Operation	Sensors	January 2023

Table 13 presents an overview of the talks at scientific conferences, seminars and forums, where D6G innovations and results have been presented between January 2023 and December 2025. Figure 20 shows a couple of talks at EuCNC 2025.

TABLE 13: DESIRE6G TALKS IN SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES AND TECHNOLOGY FORA

#	Title	Date	Description
1	LLM-Based Algorithm Selection for Network Optimization and Orchestration	15 November 2025	Anestis Dalgkitsis (UVA), SC Workshops '25 - St Louis, MO, USA
2	Road towards AI: AI4NW and NW4AI at Ericsson	7 October 2025	Gergely Pongracz (ERI-HU), Future Network Services (FNS) partner event - Delft, The Netherlands
3	Poster: FlexUP: Breaking Up the CU-UP to Speed Up the RAN	8 September 2025	Francisco Vogt, (UVA/ERI-HU), SIGCOMM 2025 - Coimbra, Portugal
4	Hierarchical Intent Decomposition Strategies for 6G Network Slicing	3 September 2025	Sultan Ertas (EBY), PIMRC 2025 - Istanbul, Turkey
5	Cloud Native IoT: Updates and Device Repurposing with K8s	26 August 2025	Anastassios Nanos and Charalampos Mainas (NUBIS), OSS EU 2025, Amsterdam
6	Experimenting Deterministic Communication Services on the Operator Side	26 July 2025	Luis M. Contreras, Marta Blanco (TID), IETF DetNet-TSN workshop - Madrid, Spain
7	DESIRE6G at IETF 123 Hackathon: Advancing Deterministic Networking with In-band Telemetry	20 July 2025	Rico-Menéndez, David; Bernardos, Carlos. J; Contreras Murillo, Luis Miguel; Blanco, Marta - IETF 123 Hackathon 2025, Madrid, Spain

8	Demo Presentation: Programmable & Trustworthy Data Paths for Sovereign Network Services	9 July 2025	Anestis Dalgkitsis (UVA), ICTON 2025 – Barcelona, Spain
9	On the Benefits of Multi-Agent Systems for Operational Expenditure Savings	7 July 2025	Marc Ruiz (UPC), ICTON 2025 – Barcelona, Spain
10	Intelligent Reconfiguration of Distributed Control of 6G Network Services	1 July 2025	Luis Velasco (UPC), OECC/PSC 2025 – Sapporo, Japan
11	Online SLA Decomposition: Enabling Real-Time Adaptation to Evolving Network Systems	4 June 2025	Cyril S. Hsu (UVA), EuCNC 2025 – Poznan, Poland
12	Unified Data Plane Layer for Next Generation Network Infrastructures	3 June 2025	Sándor Laki (ELTE), EuCNC2025 – Poznan, Poland
13	Service and Resource Management Enablers for 6G Networks – SNS Reliable SoftNet WG whitepaper	3 June 2025	George Makropoulos, EuCNC2025 – Poznan, Poland
14	From Industrial Digital Twins to Native Network Twinning: Lessons from DESIRE6G and the 6G-FNS Program	3 June 2025	Chrysa Papagianni, Integrating Network Digital Twinning into Future AI-based 6G Systems workshop, EuCNC 2025, Poznan, Poland
15	Towards an AI-native 6G system architecture	May 2025	Chrysa Papagianni, IA382 – Online Seminar in Computer Engineering at FEEC - Universidade Estadual de Campinas
16	RAILS: Risk-Aware Iterated Local Search for Joint SLA Decomposition and Service Provider Management in Multi-Domain Networks	21 May 2025	Cyril S. Hsu (UVA), HPSR 2025 – Osaka, Japan
17	From service-centric towards goal-oriented networks	20 May 2025	Gergely Pongracz (ERI-HU), 6G Programmable Deterministic Webinar Series #3
18	The Dawn of AI-Native Networks and Transforming Connectivity with AI-as-a-Service	11 December 2024	Merve Saimler (EBY), Sabanci University, Istanbul, Turkey
19	Lightweight INT on the Tofino Programmable Switch	28 November 2024	Angelos Dimoglis (UVA), 6G-PDN #2 Workshop, MobiCom24
20	Recent Results in Semantics-Native Communication and Protocol Learning in 6G	20 November 2024	Mehdi Bennis (UOU), IEEE MECOM 2024 – Abu Dhabi, UAE
21	Enhancements towards management of time-sensitive networks	22 October 2024	Sándor Laki (ELTE), 6G Programmable Deterministic Webinar Series #2

22	Semantics-native Communication and Protocol Learning in the 6G Era	21 October 2024	Mehdi Bennis (UOU), 6GNet 2024 – Paris, France
23	Expose Hardware Acceleration Functionality for Secure and Efficient Execution in Cloud Environments	27 August 2024	Anastassios Nanos (NUBIS), 19th Workshop on Virtualization in High-Performance Cloud Computing (VHPC), EURO-PAR 2024 and FOSSCOMM 2024
24	5GDAD: A Deep Learning Approach for DDoS Attack Detection in 5G P4-based UPF	24 July 2024	Francesco Paolucci (CNIT), HPSR 2024 – Pisa, Italy
25	Towards extreme network KPIs with programmability in 6G	14 June 2024	Chrysa Papagianni (UvA), at the 6G Programmable Deterministic Webinar Series
26	Autonomous LLM agents for cybersecurity and more	5 June 2024	Roberto González (NEC), Data Week 2024 in Belgium
27	Network Telemetry short course at the SSSA Seasonal School	5 June 2024	Andrea Sgambelluri (SSSA), “ARTIST - Pervasive ARTificial Intelligence for Next-G Softwarized neTworks”
28	Towards extreme network KPIs with programmability in 6G	3 June 2024	Gergely Pongracz (ERI-HU), Architecture WS, EuCNC24
29	Exploring Kata-Containers: Enhancing Cloud Security and Performance	3 June 2024	Anastassios Nanos (NUBIS), OpenInfra Days Hungary 2024
30	Intelligence for IOT Networks Towards Reliability, Robustness, And Beyond	24 May 2024	Sumudu Samarakoon (UOU), AIOT24
31	QKD endpoint software security: A talk to better grasp attacks plausibility and their remediations.	7 May 2024	Vincent Lefebvre (TSS), ONDM24. QKD workshop.
32	DESIRE6G - Distributed Genuine Intelligence for 6G	28 March 2024	Vincent Lefebvre (TSS), INCYBER24
33	Deployment of Secure Machine Learning Pipelines for Near-Real-Time Control of 6G Network Services	26 March 2024	Pol González, (UPC), OFC24
34	Distributed Multi-Agent System fed with Telemetry Data for Near-Real-Time Service Operation	26 March 2024	Marc Ruiz (UPC), OFC24
35	Unikernels in K8s: Performance and Isolation for Serverless Computing with Knative	22 March 2024	Ioannis Plakas and Anastassios Nanos (NUBIS), KUBECON24

36	Performance evaluation of Private and Public Blockchains for multi-cloud service federation	26 February 2024	Adam Zahir (UC3M), ICDCN24
37	From Containers to Unikernels: Navigating Integration Challenges in Cloud-Native Environments	3 February 2024	Georgios Ntoutsos and Ioannis Plakas (NUBIS), FOSDEM24
38	A Modular Approach to Effortless and Dependency-Aware Unikernel Building	3 February 2024	Charalampos Mainas and Anastassios Nanos (NUBIS), FOSDEM24
39	Towards extreme network KPIs with programmability in 6G (Hexa-X-II WS)	26 January 2024	Gergely Pongracz (ERI-HU), online workshop by Hexa-X-II
40	DESIRE6G - a 6G Architecture Based on Deeply Programmable Networks	6 December 2023	Sandor Laki (ELTE), 6G Work Group of Hungarian 5G Coalition
41	Pályázói tapasztalatok: a Horizon Europe 6G SNS programban	5 December 2023	Sandor Laki (ELTE), 4 th Preparatory workshop for the Hungarian EU presidency
42	Attesting What and How? Novel Forms of Attestations	15 November 2023	Vincent Lefebvre (TSS), Attestation Workshop at ORANGE Applied Cryptography Group
43	Towards extreme network KPIs with programmability in 6G	23 October 2023	Chrysa Papagianni (UvA), 6G-PDN Workshop at MobiHoc23
44	In-Network Quality Control of IP Camera Streams	23 October 2023	Csaba Györgyi (ELTE), 6G-PDN Workshop at MobiHoc23
45	Edge Intelligence over Wireless: Present & Future	9 October 2023	Mehdi Bennis (UOU), Siemens EDA Forum Finland 23
46	On the way to 6G - Distributed intelligent control, Deep programmability and Hardware acceleration	9 October 2023	Sandor Laki (ELTE), WG meeting of Hungarian Scientific Association for Infocommunications (HTE)
47	Integration of Network Slice Controller for Enhanced Intent-Based Networking in 5G/6G Networks	6 October 2023	Alejandro Muñoz (TID), Mobility in the Evolving Internet Architecture workshop (MobiArch) MobiCom23
48	DESIRE6G presentation at SNS JU Steering Board meeting	5 September 2023	Chrysa Papagianni (UvA), Athens
49	Comparison of Statistical and Machine Learning Based Approaches for Telemetry Data Size Reduction	3 July 2023	Marc Ruiz (UPC), ICTON23
50	A brief Introduction to DESIRE6G - A 6G Architecture based on deeply programmable networks	22 June 2023	Sándor Laki (ELTE), Plenary meeting of 5G Coalition, Budapest
51	Employing deep programmability and distributed intelligence for real-time 6G networks	6 June 2023	Chrysa Papagianni (UvA), The 6G series workshop at EuCNC23

52	End-to-end data plane abstraction for supporting deep slicing in 6G	6 June 2023	Sándor Laki (ELTE), Future deterministic programmable networks for 6G at EuCNC23
53	Programmability and Distributed Intelligence: a way towards predictability?	10 May 2023	Gergely Pongracz (ERI-HU), ONDM23 workshop
54	6G SNS Official start DESIRE6G presentation	23 February 2023	Chrysa Papagianni (UvA), SNS JU Lunchtime Webinars

FIGURE 20: C. HSU (LEFT) AND C. PAPAGIANNI (UVA) (RIGHT) PRESENTING AT EUCNC 2025

Events

In the table below we highlight the most relevant events attended or organized by the project or partners in relation to their work in DESIRE6G.

TABLE 14: OTHER EVENTS ATTENDED OR ORGANIZED (MIGHT BE REPEATED IN OTHER TABLES)

Date	Item	Partner
December 2025	2 nd Advisory Board Workshop with Profs. John Baras, Christian Rothenberg and Kurt Tutschku	UVA, ERI-HU, TID, NUBIS, CNIT, UPC, UC3M, NVIDIA
November 2025	General public Research Fair hosted by ETSIT- UPM as part of "UPM Conecta". Diego Rivera and Manuel Álvarez-Campana (UPM) presented DESIRE6G at their booth in Madrid, Spain	UPM
October 2025	N2WOMEN Panel: AI/ML for the Next Generation Wireless Networks by Women in Communications Engineering (WICE). Chrysa Papagianni (UVA) was one of the panelists in Marrakesh, Morocco at WiMob 2025	UVA

September 2025	Demo booth at IEEE International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC 2025)	EBY
July 2025	Co-organized IETF 123 Hackathon challenge in Madrid	UC3M, TID
June 2025	“Panel of the future of dependable networking” at EuCNC 2025. Chrysa Papagianni (UVA) was one of the panelists in PREDICT-6G’s final event	UVA
May 2025	Co-organizer of the 6G Programmable Deterministic Webinar Series #3: “Next challenges in 6G for programmable and deterministic networks”	UC3M, ERI-HU
February 2025	P4 workshop on Programmable Networks “Introduction to Data Plane Programmability”	TID, ELTE
January 2025	Organization of Journal of Optical Communications and Networking (JCON) Special Issue “Optical Networks, Systems, and Technologies for Future Radio Access”	SSSA
October 2024	Co-organizer of the 6G Programmable Deterministic Webinar Series #2: “Enhancements towards management of time-sensitive networks”	ELTE, UC3M
June 2024	Co-organization of 2 nd 6G-PDN workshop for MobiCom24	UVA, UC3M
June 2024	Participated in “Mobile Networks Evolution Day” by Telefónica	UC3M
June 2024	Participated in “Architectural Considerations Enabling the IMT 2030 Framework by European 6G R&D Activities” workshop	UC3M
June 2024	Organization of Special Issue in IEEE Network: “Deterministic, Reliable, Resilient and Programmable Networks for 6G”	UC3M, UVA
October 2023	Co-organized 6G-PDN Workshop at MobiHoc 2023	UVA
June 2023	Co-organization of IEEE NetSoft 2023 conference in Madrid	UC3M
June 2023	Participated in the Kick off of the Unikernels Alliance in Aachen	NUBIS
June 2023	Co-organized Workshop at EuCNC2023	UVA, UC3M

FIGURE 21: M. BLANCO AT IETF 123 DETNET HACKATON (LEFT), S. ERTAS DEMO BOOTH AT PIMRC 2025 (RIGHT)

Demonstrations

Besides the two main project demos (Demo 1: Augmented Reality with perceived zero latency, and Demo 2: Real-time Digital Twins), which have been presented at different stages in EuCNC 2023, 2024 and 2025, in total, 22 demos and PoCs have been shown in different events.

TABLE 15: DEMOS PRODUCED DURING PROJECT LIFETIME

#	Date	Demo title	Dissemination activity
1	November 2025	Demo 2: Real time Digital Twins (simplified version)	Example of 6G service and the 5TONIC capabilities during a private event organized by Ericsson Spain
2	November 2025	Demo 2: Real time Digital Twins (simplified version)	Example of 6G service and features during a visit of the Major of the city of Leganés (where the 5TONIC testbed is located)
3	October 2025	PoC I Zero Penalty Self-contained Binary Performance Monitoring (TSS)	This Proof of Concept (PoC) video developed by Alexis, Mark and Vincent from TSS details how software performance can be obtained using the technique of self-contained monitoring, without dependence

4	September 2025	Demo 1 AR demonstration	Augmented Reality application presented for public at the 2025 Internet Festival, Pisa, Italy
5	September 2025	Demo 1 selected workflows	In-band control and MAS workflows shown at IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking (CSCN), 15-17 September 2025, Bologna, Italy
6	September 2025	Hierarchical Intent Decomposition Strategies for 6G Network Slicing - Demo booth at IEEE PIMRC 2025	This PoC demonstrates intent-decomposition strategies; decompositions can be derived using various metrics and methods within Hierarchical Intent Decomposition. The booth was presented by Sultan Ertaş (EBY) in Istanbul, Türkiye
7	June 2025	Multi-domain PREDICT-6G DESIRE6G joint demo at EuCNC 2025	This demo, precursor of the final demo II, shows the integration of a PREDICT-6G domain with a DESIRE6G domain in and end-to-end robotic use case
8	June 2025	D-MUTRA video demo at EuCNC 2025	Video demonstrator about D-MUTRA showing the latest developments at the time of EuCNC 2025
9	March 2025	Demo I Digital Sovereignty in Practice OFC 2025	Dr. Anestis Dalgkitis presents a PoC developed by the University of Amsterdam (UvA) in collaboration with CIENA, showcasing a “Responsible Internet” architecture. Presented at OFC 2025
10	February 2025	PoC: ML assisted resource management in heterogeneous multi reflecting intelligent surface	This PoC focuses on edge intelligence and highlights ML-assisted resource management, including both training and deployment processes, based on GLOBECOM 2023 publication [4].
11	January 2025	Real time Digital Twins	Presented to delegates of the Ministry of Digitalization of Spain during a visit to 5TONIC
12	October 2024	PoC: Zero-Touch, Platform-Agnostic, Blockchain-based, Remote Attestation	Solid Shield (TSS) explains how we leverage Remote Attestation in DESIRE6G, both before execution (in Demo 1) and during execution (as a PoC)

13	September 2024	Demo 2: Real-time Digital Twins	Full demo video
14	September 2024	Demo 1: Augmented Reality with perceived zero latency	Full demo video
15	July 2024	Demo: In-network Control for Flow Steering – Scenario 1 and Demo: In-network Control for Flow Steering – Scenario 2	Demo (scenarios 1 and 2) presented by Angelos Dimoglis and Anestis Dalgkitis at ICTON2024 demo zone
16	June 2024	D6G Demo 2: Real Time Digital Twin	Preliminary version
17	June 2024	D6G Demo 1: AR with Perceived Zero Latency	Preliminary version at EuCNC2024, in preparation for full demo in ICTON2024 demo zone
18	March/ June 2024	D6G Demo: In-network Control for Flow Steering	Early version demonstrated at OFCnet booth 923. Also presented at ICTON2024 Demo Zone
19	March 2024	Demo: Deployment of Secure Machine Learning Pipelines for Near-Real-Time Control of 6G Network Services	Presented to the Advisory Board in April 2024 and at the OFC24 demo zone (video here). Slides presentation here
20	March 2024	Demo: Distributed Multi-Agent System fed with Telemetry Data for Near-Real-Time Service Operation	Presented to the Advisory Board in April 2024 and at the OFC24 demo zone. Video available here
21	March 2024	Real time Digital Twins	Presented to delegates of regional government of the region of Madrid and the Uc3M president during a visit to 5TONIC
22	January 2024	Real time Digital Twins	Presented to delegates of the Ministry of Defense of Spain during a visit to 5TONIC

2.2.2. Synergies with other projects

The following table reports collaborative activities with other EU and international research projects towards a coordinated action inside the SNS JU, from June 2023 to June 2024. As an example, Figure 22 shows the joint booth co-organized with PREDICT-6G and MultiX for EuCNC2025 in Poznan, Poland.

TABLE 16: COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITIES WITH EU AND INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH PROJECTS

Date	Item	Explanation
October 2025	Future Network Services (FNS) Dutch National 6G Conference	ERI-HU presented some of their work in DESIRE6G and FNS
July 2025	DESIRE6G at IETF 123 Hackathon: Advancing Deterministic Networking with In-band Telemetry	The IETF 123 Hackathon was held on the 19 and 20 July 2025 in Madrid, Spain. DESIRE6G project took part in the IETF 123 Hackathon in Madrid, in collaboration with PREDICT-6G and 6G-DATADRIVEN-04
June 2025	UNIPAMPA (SMARTNESS) - University of Amsterdam Workop	UVA presented their work in DESIRE6G and FNS
June 2025	6G-DATADRIVEN results and synergies	During the F2F meeting in Pisa
June 2025	DESIRE6G at EuCNC & 6G Summit 2025	Joint Booth, alongside PREDICT-6G and MultiX
March 2025	"Towards 6G Architecture: Key Concepts, Challenges, and Building Blocks" whitepaper	6G SNS Architecture WG with contributions from UC3M, ERI-HU, UPC, TSS, EBY, ELTE and UVA
February 2025	"6G KPIs - Definitions and Target Values" whitepaper	CNIT and SSSA contributed to 6G SNS Test, Measurement, and KPIs Validation (TMV) WG
January 2025	"Innovative Approaches for 6G Security: Challenges, Solutions, and Impact" whitepaper	6G-IA Security WG, with contributions from UC3M, TSS, and UPC
January 2025	"AI/ML as a Key Enabler of 6G Networks" whitepaper	UVA was co-editor and contributor to the whitepaper by 6G SNS Technology Board (TB)
December 2024	"Sustainability of 6G: Ways to Reduce Energy Consumption" whitepaper	Co-lead editor of this 6G-IA whitepaper on sustainability aspects of 6G
December 2024	"Network & Service Management Advancements" whitepaper	ELTE, UVA, UPC, and ACC contributed to this whitepaper by 6G SNS Reliable Software Networks WG. ELTE was invited to present it at EuCNC2025

November 2024	6G-DATADRIVEN results and discussion of potential joint dissemination opportunities	During the F2F meeting in Amsterdam
November 2024	“European Vision for the 6G Network Ecosystem” white paper (v2)	Co-lead editor of this 6G-IA whitepaper on the European vision on 6G
October 2024	“Enhancements towards management of time-sensitive networks”	A joint webinar with DESIRE6G, PREDICT6G and DETERMINISTIC6G
June 2024	6G-PDN Workshop: 6G Programmable Deterministic Networking with AI	Co-organized by C. Papagianni (UvA) with PREDICT-6G and DETERMINISTIC6G at MobiCom 2024, Washington DC, USA
14 June 2024	“Architectural enhancements for 6G programmable and deterministic networks”	1 st event of a webinar series with PREDICT-6G and DETERMINISTIC6G
3 June 2024	“Hyper Reliable and Low-Latency Communications for Robotics”	Joint presentation for IMT 2030 WS at EuCNC2024, with FLEXCALE, DETERMINISTIC-6G, PREDICT-6G, ETHER, and 6G-SANDBOX
3 June 2024	“Secure, Reliable and Trustworthy AI and Communication in 6G”	Joint presentation for IMT 2030 WS at EuCNC2024, with SEASON, VERGE, RIGOUROUS, and HORSE
3 – 6 June 2024	“Programmable deterministic networking: the PREDICT-6G and DESIRE6G approaches”	Joint booth at EuCNC 2024 with PREDICT-6G in Antwerp, Belgium.
26 January 2024	Online workshop on 6G by Hexa-X-II	Technical workshop organized by Hexa-X-II, together with seven other SNS JU projects
23 November 2023	Info Day & 6G SNS JU 2024 Brokerage	Event with Phase 1 success story presentation in Istanbul, Türkiye
23 October 2023	6G-PDN Workshop: 6G Programmable Deterministic Networking with AI	Co-organized by C. Papagianni (UvA) with PREDICT-6G at MobiHoc 2023, Washington DC, USA
6 June 2023	“Future deterministic programmable networks for 6G” Workshop	Co-organized with PREDICT-6G and DETERMINISTIC6G at EuCNC 2023
10 May 2023	“Challenges of optical communications in the 6G era” Workshop	6 EU projects discussed their approach to optical communications in 6G at ONDM 2023
24 March 2023	Inteligencia Artificial en el control remoto de un brazo robótico.	Joint scientific dissemination activity for high school students, with PREDICT-6G, Hexa-X-II, 6G-EDGEDT and 6G-DATADRIVEN

FIGURE 22: JOINT BOOTH WITH PREDICT-6G AND MULTI-X AT EUCNC2025. COORDINATOR C. PAPAGIANNI PRESENTS FOR SNS OFFICERS (LEFT), DESIRE6G PHD STUDENTS (RIGHT)

FIGURE 23: TECHNICAL COORDINATOR G. PONGRACZ SPEAKS AT FUTURE NETWORK SERVICES (FNS) EVENT 2025

2.2.3. Bachelor, Master, PhD Theses, and Internships

The following table reports bachelor, master and PhD theses on matters related to DESIRE6G.

TABLE 17: DESIRE6G-RELATED BACHELOR, MASTER AND PHD THESES

#	Type (PhD/Master/Int.)	Partner	State (Ongoing /Finished)	Title
1	PhD	UPC	Finished	Ahmad El Sayed, “Smart and efficient sensor network operation for 5G and beyond ecosystems”

2	PhD	UC3M	Ongoing	Carlos Barroso, "Enhanced, time sensitive, reliable and available wireless networks based on AI"
3	PhD	UC3M	Ongoing	Pablo Picazo, "Development of reliable SDN-based wireless and virtualization technologies for real-time scenarios"
4	PhD	UC3M	Ongoing	Adam Zahir, "Blockchain Solutions and Advanced Mechanisms for 6G Networks and Future Applications"
5	PhD	UC3M	Ongoing	Alejandro Calvillo, "Graph-Based Modelling and Optimization for Telecommunication Networks"
6	MSc	UC3M	Finished	Adam Zahir "Diseño y Desarrollo de un Gemelo Digital para un Robot Cuadrúpedo con Simulación en Tiempo Real"
7	BSc	UVA	Finished	Jan Laan, "Extending a simulation framework for virtualised infrastructures"
8	BSc	UVA	Finished	Merijn Laks, "VFNet a simulation framework for orchestration virtualised infrastructures"
9	BSc	UVA	Finished	Tim van der Hoeven, "Evaluation Platform for In-band network telemetry solutions"
10	BSc	UVA	Finished	Hakan Bektas "Intelligent Traffic Steering Using Reinforcement Learning"
11	MSc	UVA	Finished	Gesualdo Di Perna, "P4-Driven Offloading of O-RAN O-CU-UP Functionalities on SmartNICs"
12	MSc	UVA	Finished	Ralph Erkamps, "Enhancing Network Telemetry Applications Through Data Plane Processing with a P4 Collector"
13	MSc, RP2	UVA	Finished	Wendy Rok "O-RAN: Design & Implementation of the Central Unit on a SmartNIC with XDP/eBPF"
14	MSc	UVA	Finished	Diogo Mateus Moreira Benzinho Marque, "Service-Specific Multi-Agent System Deployment for Scalable 6G Architectures Using K8S and VXLAN"
15	MSc, RP1	UVA	Finished	Tomas Agata, "Exploring Programmable Network Techniques for Data Plane Optimization"

16	MSc, RP2	UVA	Finished	Tomas Agata, Design and Integration of a Smart Orchestrator for 6G Services
17	MSc, RP1	UVA	Finished	Muhammad Mansour, “Exploring Programmable Network Techniques for Data Plane Optimization”
18	MSc, RP2	UVA	Finished	Muhammad Mansour, “Design and Integration of a Smart Orchestrator for 6G Services”
19	MSc	UVA, Polito	Finished	Luca Cetino, “Evaluation of FPGA-based In-band Telemetry Methodologies for the Responsible Internet”
20	PhD	UVA	Finished	Cyril Hsu, “Machine Learning for Network Slice Management
21	PhD	UVA	Ongoing	Angelo Dimoglis, “Data-plane programmability towards a transparent, reliable and controllable Internet”
22	PhD	UVA, UMD	Ongoing	Asim Zoukarni, “Security and Resource Allocation for Edge and Autonomous Systems”
23	PhD	UVA	Ongoing	Jose Zerna, “An AI-assisted In-band Network Telemetry Framework”
24	MSc	UOU	Finished	Chamith Mawela: “A Web-Based Solution for Federated Learning with LLM-Based Automation”
25	MSc	UOU	Finished	Athmajan Vivekananthan: “Adaptive autonomy in multi-agent systems with modeled interactions: an empirical analysis”
26	PhD	ELTE	Ongoing	Hiba Mallouhi: “Foundations of Zero-Touch Computer Networks”
27	PhD	ELTE	Ongoing	Dávid Kis: “Advanced traffic engineering in telecommunication networks with the support of PPOV”
28	PhD	ELTE	Ongoing	Károly Kecskeméti: “Data plane optimizations”
29	PhD	ELTE	Finished	Csaba Györgyi: Application of programmable data planes with the P4 language in industrial environments
30	MSc	ELTE	Finished	Ádám Farkas: Congestion signal-based load balancing between network paths (Hungarian, original title: Torlódásjelzés alapú terheléelosztás útvonalak között)

31	PhD	SSSA/CNIT/ NVIDIA	Finished	Faris Alhamed: PhD program in Emerging Digital Technologies (funded by NVIDIA)
32	PhD	SSSA/CNIT/ NVIDIA	Ongoing	Rana Abu Bakar: PhD program in Emerging Digital Technologies (funded by NVIDIA)
33	PhD	SSSA	Finished	Alessandro Pacini: A flexible and modular approach towards Zero Touch Networks
34	PhD	SSSA	Ongoing	Layal Ismail: PhD program in Emerging Digital Technologies
35	MSc	EBY	Ongoing	Selin Tipi: “Leveraging LLMs for Intelligent Telecommunications Management”
36	MSc	UPM	Ongoing	Silvia Mauleon: “Design and implementation of a programmable SDN control architecture for deterministic networks over P4-based Tofino switches”

All the academic partners in DESIRE6G incorporate the work and results stemming from the project in their academic curricula, as described in their exploitations plans in D6.6 Exploitation Strategy Report 2 [5]. Figure 24 below shows Marc Ruiz teaching in UPC, Barcelona sharing the latest projects results with his students. On the right, Andrea Sgambelluri presents in ARTIST 5G/6G Season school in SSSA, which has taken place every summer from 2023 to 2025 in Pisa, focusing on pervasive monitoring and P4 INT for deep service monitoring developed in DESIRE6G.

FIGURE 24: M. RUIZ (UPC) GIVES A LECTURE IN DEC 2025 (LEFT). A. SGAMBELLURI TEACHES WP4 CONTENT IN ARTIST 5G/6G SEASONAL SCHOOL (SSSA) (RIGHT)

2.3. Standardization and Open Source

The target for the DESIRE6G project was 10 contributions to SDOs, such as 3GPP, IETF, ETSI, IEEE, O-RAN, ITU over the lifetime of the project. By the end of the project specific actions and contributions have been produced for IETF, 3GPP, ETSI and O-RAN, in relation with technical aspects of relevance for the project, where D6G activities have served as input. The following table summarizes all the current SDO activities and contributions done during the lifetime of the project (some of them already adopted or accepted).

TABLE 18: CURRENT SDO ACTIVITIES AND CANDIDATE CONTRIBUTIONS

#	SDO	Type of Document (Contribution / Dissemination)	Partner	Link to Candidate contribution
1	IETF (DetNet WG)	Contribution (<u>adopted</u>)	UC3M	https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-detnet-controller-plane-framework/06/
2	IETF (DetNet WG)	Contribution on multidomain support	UC3M	https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-bernardos-detnet-raw-multidomain/02/
3	O-RAN (WG9)	Contribution on DetNet overview as discussion input for the Xhaul packet switching specification	TID	https://oranalliance.atlassian.net/wiki/pages/viewpageattachments.action?pagelid=2653487497&preview=%2F2653487497%2F2774335856%2FTEF-2023.02.06-WG9-XPAAS-DetNet-v0.pptx&search_id=9e0b9630-e3fa-435e-bcfb-6df1c7a37452
4	3GPP (SA5)	Contribution to improve EP_Transport model of TS 28.541 in Release 18 to clarify connection point for network slicing when interworking with transport networks	TID	https://www.3gpp.org/ftp/tsg_sa/WG5_TM/TSGS5-149/Docs/S5-234742.zip
5	IETF (DetNet WG)	Contribution. An Evolution of Cooperating Layered Architecture for SDN (CLAS) for Compute and Data Awareness	UC3M, TID	https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-contreras-coinrq-clas-evolution/02
6	IETF (DetNet WG)	Contribution on relevant use cases (<u>adopted</u>)	UC3M	https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-detnet-raw-industrial-req/00

7	3GPP SA2	Contribution. FS_eEDGE_5GC_Ph3 / Rel-19	ERI-HU	https://www.3gpp.org/ftp/tsg_sa/WG2_Arch/TSGS2_162_Changsha_2024-04/Docs/S2-2404482.zip
8	O-RAN (WG1 – WG9)	Contribution. WG9-2024.001 Work Item Proposal – Inclusion of Transport in SMO (<u>accepted and created</u>).	TID	Not available publicly (file name: VZW.AO-2024.05.31-WG9-D-Transport-Inclusion-Data_Exposure)
9	ETSI	Contribution. Contribute to define intent related optional operations (JUDGE, BEST, and PROBE)	EBY	Not available publicly (https://docbox.etsi.org/ISG/ZSM/Open/Drafts/016_IntentDrvCL/ZSM-016_IntentDrvCLv0010.zip)
10	IETF	Contribution. A PCE-based Control Plane Framework for Multi-Domain Deterministic Networking (DetNet)	UC3M	https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-bernardos-detnet-multi-domain-pce/
11	IETF	Contribution. DetNet multidomain extensions.	UC3M	https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-bernardos-detnet-raw-multidomain/
12	IETF	Contribution. Computing Aware Traffic Steering using IP address anchoring.	UC3M	https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-bernardos-cats-ip-address-anchoring/
13	IETF	Contribution. A Framework for Deterministic Networking (DetNet) Controller Plane.	UC3M	https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-detnet-controller-plane-framework/
14	IETF	Contribution. Enhanced Use Cases for Scaling Deterministic Networks.	TID	https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-zhao-detnet-enhanced-use-cases/
15	IETF	Contribution. Using Deterministic Networks for Industrial Operations and Control.	TID	https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-km-detnet-for-ocn/
16	IETF / IEEE	Dissemination. Experimenting Deterministic Communication Services on the Operator Side (Dissemination).	TID	https://1.ieee802.org/2025-07-26-detnet-tsn-workshop/
17	3GPP	Contribution. Method where the SMO or the NF itself could report its current and anticipated energy consumption to the consumer NFs to facilitate a more energy efficient NF (re-)selection.	ERI-HU	https://www.3gpp.org/ftp/tsg_sa/WG2_Arch/TSGS2_169_Fukuoka_2025-05/Docs/S2-2504896.zip

Regarding Open-Source contributions, Table 19 reports all the contributions made so far. Additionally, some pieces of the DESIRE6G stack are available as open source in the project Github repository: <https://github.com/DESIRE6G>.

TABLE 19: OPEN-SOURCE CONTRIBUTIONS SINCE JANUARY 2023, SUBMITTED AND ACCEPTED

#	Community and Title	Info	Partner	Link
1	ETSI TFS SDG	Driver for P4 configuration of Tofino switches to enable PREOF functionality from centralized SDN controller	UPM	Planned for next TFS release in March 2026
2	kata-containers runtime-rs: Use vCPU and memory values from config	Use values from the config for the setup of the microVM. Fixes: #10434	NUBIS	https://github.com/kata-containers/kata-containers/pull/10435
3	kata-containers runtime-rs: Fix QEMU backend for runtime-rs	It seems that PR #8070 broke QEMU for runtime-rs.	NUBIS	https://github.com/kata-containers/kata-containers/pull/10052
4	kata-containers runtime-rs: add parameter for propagation of (u)mount events	code to facilitate AWS Firecracker execution in sandboxed container runtimes. Accepted.	NUBIS	https://github.com/kata-containers/kata-containers/commit/6787c63900c6d4dc2de903a076f3230ecec4259b
5	containerd	filesystem support for containerd to allow rumprun unikernels to execute Code merged in 2023, included in containerd v1.7.0 release. Accepted.	NUBIS	https://github.com/containerd/containerd/releases/tag/v1.7.0
6	Unikraft: Update GICv2 compatible list	Enable Unikraft unikernels to be executed on aarch64 nodes (such as low-power edge nodes). Accepted.	NUBIS	https://github.com/unikraft/unikraft/commit/404c280443c1caec7027924973c64a9aa3f78dd6
7	kata-containers runtime-rs: update rust to 1.69.0	Helper contribution to support easier building of sandboxed container	NUBIS	https://github.com/kata-containers/kata-containers/commit/e4eb664d27f6cf7169c5d10f4383bdd8f3b892f6

		runtime (kata-containers) Accepted.		
8	kata-containers runtime-rs: Firecracker hypervisor backend	Support AWS Firecracker on the rust runtime. Pending.	NUBIS	https://github.com/kata-containers/kata-containers/pull/8070

Open-source involvement

NUBIS has been actively involved in the open-source ecosystem (see Table 19) with notable contributions to the Kata Containers project, the only mature sandboxed container runtime, and a significant initiative under the OpenInfra Foundation. Highlighting this involvement, Anastassios Nanos, WP3 leader, from NUBIS, has been elected² to the Architecture Committee of Kata Containers. This committee, responsible for architectural decisions and maintaining the project's governance, embodies the "four opens": open source, open design, open development, and open community. Dr Nanos' involvement in the Kata containers AC is a testament DESIRE6G commitment to fostering diversity, openness, and encouraging new contributors within the open-source community.

Furthermore UPM, in collaboration with TID, has been working on a P4 driver for ETSI TFS to enable centralized control configuration of advance reliable capabilities such as PREOF. The integration of this driver is work in progress with the expectation of being available next March 2026 in a forthcoming release of ETSI TFS.

² <https://github.com/kata-containers/community?tab=readme-ov-file#architecture-committee>

2.4. Project reach

Involvement in SNS JU activities related to standardization and open source DESIRE6G has participated in the Pre-Standardization WG of the 6G-IA. The project provided an overview of the contributions to standardization and pre-standardization work during the regular meeting of December 2025.

2.4.1. Engagement with other initiatives

Below we report engagements with external projects, initiatives and individuals, who have approached DESIRE6G members either in person or digitally, interested in the work that the project has carried out. The outcomes of these interactions have resulted in dissemination of DESIRE6G's innovations and in establishing collaborations of different nature, i.e.: workshops, student placements, hackathons, open source contributions, research programs, etc.

TABLE 20: ENGAGEMENT WITH EXTERNALS

Name/ Affiliation	Engagement	Who	When	Outcome
Chrysa Papagianni/ UVA	Overview on DESIRE6G context (architecture, technologies etc.)	Fernando Kuipers/ TUDelft	2023	Involvement of UVA in 6G FNS (NL growth funds project) leading AI-assisted networking.
Chrysa Papagianni/ UVA	Enquired on DESIRE6G in-band network telemetry and ML for scaling of edge resources.	Fabio Verdi/ UFSCar Sorocaba	Jan 2024	Two BSc students were hosted by UVA for research internships on related topics.
Teresa Calafat/ UVA	Approached via contact@desire6g.eu to join EuCNC25 workshop on Digital Twinning	Sébastien Faye and Régis Decorme, 6G-TWIN	Dec 24	Contact resulted in accepted joint workshop with 7 SNS JU projects
Chrysa Papagianni/ UVA	Enquired on trustworthiness aspects of architecture, notably cybersecurity requirements, design and implementation aspects for 6G	Panos Papadimitratos, KTH	April 2025	Bootstrapping of collaboration at the intersection of 6G and scalable credential management and secure route discovery and data communication

Chrysa Papagianni/ UVA	DESIRE6G EUCNC 2025	N2WOMEN	Sep 2025	Invitation to WICE/N2Women Panel on AI/ML for Next Generation Wireless Networks at IEEE WiMob
Chrysa Papagianni/ UVA	Presentation of CU-UP offloading to DPU's and related topics	Marc Makkes, Head of Product & Innovation, Fortaegis	Nov 2025	Dr Makkes will become a guest researcher at MNS-UVA starting from 2026.
Chrysa Papagianni/ UVA	Enquired on DESIRE6G data plane programmability research and ML for scaling of edge resources.	Leandro Almeida and Ruan Delgado Gomes, Instituto Federal da Paraba	Nov 2025	Dr. Gomes will be hosted for a year (2026) to conduct collaborative research on "Quality of Service of Critical Video Applications through Programmable Networks in Edge Computing Environments"
Chrysa Papagianni/ UVA	Exchange of research results on ML for network automation	Carla Chiasserini/ PoliTo	Dec 25	Potential research collaboration on related topics.
Vincent Lefebvre/ TSS	Contact for PoC with ORANGE France and related to D-MUTRA	ORANGE lab France	Jan 25	The PoC shall reveal the relevance of D-MUTRA to be used to bring security to ORANGE off-premises deployed NFs
Vincent Lefebvre/ TSS	SNS JU program head (deputy) and representatives from research organizations had questions about D-MUTRA during EuCNC25	Pavlos Fournogerakis, and others	June 25	Presented D-MUTRA's key benefits for future 6G service security
Vincent Lefebvre/ TSS	Approached during EuCNC about ETSI open source for networking	Sylvia Almagia	June 25	First talk to consider placing D-MUTRA as an open source solution, held at ETSI
Manuel lvarez-Campana/ UPM	Participation on ETSI Teraflow SDN Hackfest #7 in Castelldefels, Barcelona. Contribution to open challenges related to new	Shayan Hajipour (CTTC), Pablo Golderos (TID), David de la Osa (TID)	May 19 - May 22 2025	Contribution to new features of the Slice Network Controller component developed by TID

	Network Slice Control component.			
Manuel Álvarez-Campana / UPM	Meeting with representatives of Teraflow SDN related to possible contribution to P4 module for supporting native Tofino BFRT runtime protocol.	Georgios Katsikas (UBITECH), Ricard Vilalta (CTTC)	May 25	Exchange of ideas about supporting Tofino P4 switches in Teraflow SDN
Gergely Pongracz / ERI-HU	SMARTNESS project, coordinated from Brazil, reached out about WP4 (programmable networks)	Christian Esteve Rothenberg (UNICAMP)	2024	Ongoing collaboration between involved universities and Ericsson where Gergely is the industrial lead. Discussions aimed to align SMARTNESS topics better with D6G. Hosting of one PhD student at UVA.
Gergely Pongracz / ERI-HU	RAN developers from Ericsson (Sweden) asked about our work in P4 and especially our 3GPP implementations (CU-UP, DU, UPF)	Ulf Parkholm (Ericsson, RAN ASIC design specialist)	April 25	Gergely gave two presentations on the topic. The ASIC design team is also interested in detailed compiler questions, currently we are discussing the involvement of university partners (ELTE) in this specific topic
Carlos J. Bernardos / UC3M	Discussion with colleagues at UC3M working in the PREDICT-6G project, ending up in a joint hackathon project in IETF123 and demo 2 integrating both projects	Antonio de la Oliva, David Rico, PREDICT-6G	March 24	Joint hackathon project in IETF 123, final joint demo 2 of the project
Carlos J. Bernardos / UC3M	Request to share, discuss and present sustainability related aspects	Mir Ghoraiishi	March 25	Participation in a sustainability workshop at EuCNC 2025
Carlos J. Bernardos / UC3M	Request to share sustainability related aspects to explore collaborations in SUSTAIN-6G	Marco Gramaglia, SUSTAIN-6G	Feb 25	Report to SUSTAIN-6G on sustainability related activities for future coordination (SUSTAIN-

				6G is the lighthouse project related to sustainability in SNS-JU)
Carlos J. Bernardos / UC3M	Request to host two students (short and long visit) to work on P4 related aspects	Christian Esteve Rothenberg, Unicamp	Jun 25	A short visit of a week of a student working on P4 (in topics related to DESIRE6G and demo2) and a 6-month one of another one planned for next year
Gergely Pongracz / ERI-HU	3 operators (HUN, SK, AUT) attending the InnoDay asked about the details of dynamic slice deployment and its implications	T-Mobile Hungary, Orange Slovakia, Austrian Telecom	Nov 25	Presented specific DESIRE6G innovations
Diego Rivera / UPM	Meeting with Institute form Smart Electronics and Systems at FAU (Friedrich-Alexander-Universität) for presenting 5G/6G related projects	Eva Russwurm, Paulus Guter, Norman Franchi (FAU)	26/9/25	D6G participation was discussed, among other 5G/6G projects from both universities. Possible future collaborations between research groups in the universities
Diego Rivera / UPM	Presentation of research activities at Research fair (UPM)	Fair attendants (researchers, students)	18/11/25	D6G activities were presented at the fair stand. Questions regarding the research activities were answered for attendants

3. Ambitions after project completion

3.1. Communication ambitions

The following table is an update of the first version of the Communication Plan presented in D6.1 (June 2023) [3]. It includes the targeted audience, the related activities, the timing, and the metrics of the communication activities, including quantified goals.

Note that we commit to at least one year of continuation of activities (with different levels of intensity, depending on the nature of the activity) after the project completion on December 31st, 2025.

3.1.1. Communication work plan after project completion

TABLE 21: COMMUNICATION PLAN AFTER THE PROJECT COMPLETION

Audience	Activity	Timing
All, General public, Research	Project website. DESIRE6G shares its concepts, results and achievements through the project website. The website is the primary tool of communication and promotion of the project	Minor updates with relevant achievements during 2026
General public	Public Communication. DESIRE6G project is regularly being promoted through participation and organization of events for society at large and distribution through social media. We plan to make use of EC communication tools and magazines after the completion of the project	Event-driven only (during 2026)
General public, Interest groups	Videos. DESIRE6G will post on its networks (mainly the YouTube channel) videos related to demos and events where project results are shown during 2026 For RP2 we will create a partner series, where each D6G explains their role and learnings from the project	Event-driven only (during 2026)

Students	Lecture materials related with DESIRE6G will be introduced in academic courses taught by partners for the course 2025-2026.	At least during the 2025-2026 academic year
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3.2. Dissemination ambitions

The purpose of a dissemination plan is to guarantee that all concepts and technologies developed in a project are disseminated adequately to relevant entities, including standards development organizations. During 2026, once DESIRE6G has officially finished, we plan to continue executing some Dissemination and Collaboration activities (primarily within the SNS JU) to help promote the project concept and main outcomes to the large European and more International R&D community, facilitating the adoption of some concepts by other running and emerging projects. During 2026 we ambition to exploit the availability of the final experimental and validation results to be disseminated mainly through scientific publications and demonstrations. Another dissemination channel worth mentioning is the defence of academic works (e.g., PhD and MsC thesis) that include project-related results, as there are several that are planned for 2026-2029. All the dissemination results obtained in 2026 (e.g., papers accepted/published) will be uploaded to Zenodo.

3.2.1. Synergies with other projects

While most of the projects DESIRE6G has actively collaborated with end in 2025, thus limiting further activities in 2026, there are a couple of projects that we expect to adopt DESIRE6G results and use them during 2026 onwards:

- FNS (2024-2029) (<https://futurenetworkservices.nl>). The Dutch Flagship Project on 6G supported by the Minister of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy (EZK) aims at building a strategic and leading position in the development and application of 6G networks for unlocking the innovation potential of the Dutch industry, contributing to the European pre-standardization efforts, and training the next generation of engineers and researchers. The project will develop intelligent hardware and AI-driven network management schemes for 6G networks. FNS PL2 focuses on AI-assisted network automation to improve network performance and energy-efficiency, thus is highly aligned with the objectives of DESIRE6G. It also aims to build upon the IML layer of DESIRE6G for delivering a HAL. Common partners include: UVA, ERI-HU, NVIDIA.

- SLICES-RI (2017-2040) (<https://www.slices-ri.eu>). SLICES is a flexible platform designed to support large-scale, experimental research focused on networking protocols, radio technologies, services, data collection, parallel and distributed computing and in particular cloud and edge-based computing architectures and services. Some services currently offered and planned to be offered in the next months, leverage DESIRE6G outcomes and lessons learned. Common partners include: UVA, UC3M.
- SNS FLECON-6G (2025-2027) (<https://flecon6g.eu/>). The FLECON-6G project (Flexible Open Architecture and AI-driven Enabling Technologies for a Novel 6G Connectivity Platform) aims at building a scalable, intelligent 6G network based on open and flexible architecture. Its goal is to realize the vision of an Intelligent 6G Network of Networks by leveraging key technologies such as native, trustworthy and generalizable AI, Network Digital Twins, and zero-touch automated orchestration, enabling efficient operation across multi-domain and multi-stakeholder environments. FLECON-6G has a specific task dedicated to programmable platforms for data plane flow control and extreme edge integration which leverages on outcomes from DESIRE6G. Common partners include: TID, NVIDIA and CNIT.
- SMARTNESS (2022-2032) (<https://smartness2030.tech/>). The SMART NEtworks and ServiceS for 2030) FAPESP Engineering Research Center (ERC) aims to advance cutting-edge research in computer networks and digital application services focused on strategic areas where scientific and technological impacts can be achieved by the year 2030, in collaboration with research communities of cloud and networking. With SMARTNESS students hosted at the University of Amsterdam, collaborative research has been conducted between the two projects. Common partners include: ERI-HU.

3.2.2. Open Science

DESIRE6G leverages the services provided by the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe ([OpenAIRE](#)), which is an active service provider of the [European Open Science Cloud](#) (EOSC). This European initiative, which lists 37+ million publications and 9+ million research data, has the mission to promote open scholarship and improve the discoverability, accessibility, shareability, reusability, reproducibility and monitoring of data-driven research results, across scientific disciplines.

We aim to continue managing open data and access to research results during 2026 as described in D1.1 [6]. Note that this will be done on a voluntary basis, as partners cannot be contractually bounded to this once the project has finished.

3.3. Standardization ambitions

From its inception, DESIRE6G has had a clear goal of contributing to both standardization and open-source activities. During the project execution lifetime, this purpose has been perceived as a bidirectional interaction between the project and external communities. This meant that any progress in the standardization and open-source arenas could influence the development of DESIRE6G architecture and innovations, and vice versa. Once the project gets to its end, our ambition is to (i) maintain (if required) those project-related contributions that are still “alive” (e.g., adopted, but not yet published, or not-adopted but with good chances to be adopted); and (ii) evaluate if new contributions are needed, in light of the latest technical developments and consolidated outcomes of the project.

3.3.1. Open-source communities of relevance for DESIRE6G

Similarly to the approach followed for standardization activities, there is a multiplicity of OS communities of relevance for the project. Relevant OS projects cover orchestration, management and control of the network, cloud-native platforms, and device-level data-plane programmability. Different OS projects are subject to receiving contributions from DESIRE6G depending on the specific role they could play in the overall architecture, with the aim of validating the conceptual design.

Beyond the project lifetime, we plan—on a best-effort and voluntary basis—to conduct maintenance activities during 2026 for selected open-source contributions, where needed to ensure continued usability and relevance. A concrete example is the anticipated release of ETSI TFS in March 2026, which is expected to incorporate the P4 driver developed within DESIRE6G.

3.4. Project reach

To provide continued visibility on the project’s main contributions and results, we aim to sustain the dissemination of DESIRE6G achievements beyond the project lifetime. This effort will leverage the fact that many DESIRE6G partners are already involved in closely related projects that have recently started, as well as in new initiatives expected to commence in 2026. We will actively promote the proper acknowledgement in reuse of DESIRE6G concepts and results across these follow-up activities. This systematic traceability of impact will serve as a concrete instrument to demonstrate the value and long-term return of the SNS JU and, more broadly, the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme.

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